

Supplementary Appendix for: Bartolomé-Porcar, C. (2026). “Not Just ‘Tales’ of Rebel Women: Non-Fictional Reading Collections of Short Biographies for Young Readers within the Spanish Context.” *Pitfalls of Good Intentions: Exploring Textual Intentionality in Children’s and YA Literature*, edited by Élodie Malanda, Suzanne van der Beek, and Jessaline Tanjung, Malmö University Press. Document DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20641538>

Text authorship	Title	Publisher	Year	Original language	Illustration	Typology/presentation	Recommended age	Pages	Bibliography	Preliminary	Chronological axis	Image	Portagonists	Date of birth/death	Place of birth	Figure’s speech
	<i>Cuentos de buenas noches. Nuestras niñas rebeldes [Good Night Stories for Rebel Girls: Our Rebel Girls]</i>	Destino Infantil y Juvenil	2021	Spanish	VV.AA.	Narr (lineal)	6-8 yrs	2	No	Yes	No	Portrait	100	Yes/Yes	Yes (out)	Quote (out) D/I sp.
	<i>No me cuentes cuentos: 100 mujeres españolas [Don’t Tell Me Fairy Tales: 100 Spanish Women]</i>	Montena	2019	Spanish	VV.AA.	Narr (diverse)	9 yrs	4-6	No	Yes	No	Various	100	No/No	No	D / I speech
Blázquez, Carmen et al.	<i>101 Grandes mujeres de la Historia: una mirada femenina de nuestro mundo [101 Great Women in History: A Feminine Perspective on Our World]</i>	Susacta	s.f.	Spanish	-	Expositive (fragments)	From 9 yrs.	1-2	No	No	No	Figure, photos, others	101	Yes/Yes (out)	No	Quote (out)
Cívico, Irene y Sergio Parra	<i>Las chicas son guerreras. 26 rebeldes que cambiaron el mundo. [The Girls Are Warriors: 26 Rebels Who Changed the World]</i>	Montena	2016	Spanish	Aparicio, Nuria	Narr (lineal-fragments)	From 12 yrs.	4	No	No	Yes	Portrait / others	26	Yes/No (out)	Yes (out)	Quote (out) D/I sp.
Cívico, Irene y Sergio Parra	<i>Las chicas son de ciencias. 25 científicas que cambiaron el mundo [The Girls Are into Science: 25 Scientists Who Changed the World]</i>	Montena	2018	Spanish	Aparicio, Nuria	Narr (lineal-fragments)	From 12 yrs.	4	No	No	Yes	Portrait / others	25	Yes/No (out)	Yes (out)	Quote (out) D/I sp.
Cívico, Irene y Sergio Parra	<i>Las chicas van donde quieren. 25 aventureras que cambiaron el mundo [The Girls Go Where They Want: 25 Adventurers Who Changed the World]</i>	Montena	2019	Spanish	Aparicio, Nuria	Narr (lineal-fragments)	From 12 yrs.	4	No	No	Yes	Portrait / others	25	Yes/No (out)	Yes (out)	Quote (out) D/I sp.
de Aragón, Juan	<i>Heroínas secretas de la historia de España. [Secret Heroines of Spanish History]</i>	Penguin RandomHouse	2018	Spanish	de Aragón	Narr (lineal)	YAs	2	Yes	Yes	No	Portrait comic	44	Yes/Yes (out)	No	Comic dialogue
Elmert, Sandra	<i>100 mujeres que cambiaron el mundo. [100 Women Who Changed the World]</i>	Molino	2018	Spanish	Sandra González	Narr (lineal)	From 7 yrs	2	No	No	No	Portrait	100	Yes/Yes (out)	No	No
Favilli, Elena	<i>Cuentos de buenas noches para niñas rebeldes. 100 mujeres inmigrantes que han cambiado el mundo / Good Night Stories for Rebel Girls: 100 Immigrant Women Who Changed the World</i>	Destino Inf y Juv	2020	English	VV.AA.	Narr (lineal)	6-8 yrs	2	No	Yes	No	Portrait	100	Yes/Yes (out)	Yes (out)	Quote (out) D/I sp.
Favilli, Elena, y Cavallo, Elena	<i>Cuentos de buenas noches para niñas rebeldes / Good Night Stories for Rebel Girls</i>	Destino Inf y Juv	2017 (ed. or. 2016)	English	VV.AA.	Narr (lineal)	6-8 yrs	2	No	Yes	No	Portrait	100	Yes/Yes (out)	Yes (out)	Quote (out) D/I sp.
Favilli, Elena, y Cavallo, Elena	<i>Cuentos de buenas noches para niñas rebeldes 2 / Good Night Stories for Rebel Girls 2</i>	Destino Inf y Juv	2018 (ed. or. 2017)	English	VV.AA.	Narr (lineal)	6-8 yrs	2	No	Yes	No	Portrait	78	Yes/Yes (out)	Yes (out)	Quote (out) D/I sp.
Freire, Espido	<i>Pioneras: Mujeres que abrieron camino [Pioneers: Women Who Opened the Way]</i>	Anaya Infantil y Juvenil	2019	Spanish	Pérez, Helena	Narr (lineal)	From 10 yrs	2	No	Yes	No	Portrait	50	Yes/Yes (in)	Yes (in)	No
Halligan, Katherine	<i>Ellas cuentan: 50 mujeres y niñas que cambiaron el mundo [They Count: 50 Women and Girls Who Changed the World]</i>	SM	2019 (ed. 2018)	English	Walsh, Sarah	Narr (lineal-fragments)	10 a 18 yrs.	2	No	Yes	Yes	Portrait, photos, others	50	Yes/Yes (index)	Yes (in)	Quote (out)
Hodges, Kate	<i>Vidas extraordinarias: Lazos entre mujeres que han cambiado el mundo [Extraordinary Lives: Bonds Between Women Who Have Changed the World]</i>	Lunweg	2018	English	Papworth, Sarah	Narr (lineal)	-	2	No	Yes	No	Portrait, others	84	Yes/Yes (Index)	Yes (Index)	Quote (in) D sp.
Huertas, Rosa	<i>Mujeres de la cultura [Women in Culture]</i>	Anaya	2019	Spanish	Eugenia	Diverse	From 10-	No	Yes	No	Figure	10	Yes/Yes	Yes (out)	Quote (out)	

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					Abalos		12	16						(out)		D/I sp.
Ignotofsky, Rachel	<i>Mujeres de ciencia. 50 intrépidas pioneras que cambiaron el mundo / Women in Science: 50 Fearless Pioneers Who Changed the World</i>	Nórdica Cómico	2017	English	Ignotofsky, Rachel	Narr (lineal)	-	2	Yes	Yes	No	Figure	50	Yes/No (in)	Yes (in)	Quote (out)
Ignotofsky, Rachel	<i>Mujeres en el arte: 50 intrépidas creadoras que inspiraron al mundo / Women in Art: 50 Fearless Creatives Who Inspired the World</i>	Nórdica Cómico	2020	English	Ignotofsky, Rachel	Narr (lineal)	-	2	Yes	Yes	No	Figure	50	Yes/Yes (out)	Yes (in)	Quote (out)
Ignotofsky, Rachel	<i>Mujeres en el deporte: 50 valientes atletas que jugaron para ganar / Women in Sports: 50 Fearless Athletes Who Played to Win</i>	Nórdica Cómico	2018	English	Ignotofsky, Rachel	Narr (lineal)	-	2	Yes	Yes	No	Figure	50	Yes/No (in)	Yes (in)	Quote (out)
Irwin, Bindi (Prol.)	<i>Cuentos de buenas noches para niñas rebeldes. 100 jóvenes que están cambiando el mundo / Good Night Stories for Rebel Girls: 100 Inspiring Young Changemakers</i>	Destino Infantil y Juvenil	2023 (ed. or. 2022)	English	VV.AA.	Narr (lineal)	6-8 yrs	2	No	Yes	No	Portrait	100	Yes/No (out)	Yes (out)	Quote (out) D/I sp.
López, Aitziber	<i>Inventoras y sus inventos [Inventors and Their Inventions]</i>	Flamboyant	2018	Spanish	Lozano, Luciano	Exp (fragments)	YNM	2	No	No	No	Illustr.	14	Yes/No (in)	Yes (in)	No
Morán Ortí, José	<i>Ellas: 30 grandes mujeres que cambiaron el mundo [Them: 30 Great Women Who Changed the World]</i>	Susaeta	n.d.	Spanish	Anais, Marta	Narr (lineal-fragments)	From 9 yrs.	2-3	No	Yes	No	Figure / others	30	Yes/Yes (in)	Yes (in)	Quote (in), D speech
Palacios, Mercedes	<i>Visionarias: Inventoras desconocidas [Visionaries: Unknown Inventors]</i>	Bridge	2020	Spanish	Palacios, Mercedes	Narr (lineal)	-	2-6	No	Yes	Yes	Portrait, Figure, patent, others	33	Yes/No (out)	Yes (in)	Quote (in), D speech
Serret, Cristina	<i>Luchadoras [Fighters]</i>	Shackleton kids.	2021	Spanish	House, Wuji	Narr (fragments)	6 to 9 yrs	4	No	Yes	Yes	Figure / others	22	Yes/Yes (out)	Yes (out)	Quote (out)
Serret, Cristina	<i>Científicas [Scientists]</i>	Shackleton kids.	2021	Spanish	House, Wuji	Narr (fragments)	6 to 9 yrs	4	No	Yes	Yes	Figure / others	18	Yes/Yes (out)	Yes (out)	Quote (out)
Serret, Cristina	<i>Creativas [Creatives]</i>	Shackleton kids.	2020	Spanish	House, Wuji	Narr (fragments)	6 to 9 yrs	4	No	Yes	Yes	Figure / others	18	Yes/Yes (out)	Yes (out)	Quote (out)
Uve, Sandra	<i>Supermujeres, superinventoras: Ideas brillantes que transformaron nuestra vida [Superwomen, Superinventors: Brilliant Ideas That Transformed Our Lives]</i>	Lunweg	2018	Spanish	Uve, Sandra	Narr Expositive	-	2	Yes	Yes	No	Portrait / patent	93	Yes/Yes (out)	Yes (out)	No